

METHODS OF STUDYING PUBLIC OPINION

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Abstract. Public opinion is a form of collective consciousness that includes both hidden and open attitudes toward social events, the activities of various groups, organizations, and individuals. It manifests in the approval or condemnation of specific social issues, defines the behavior of individuals and social groups, and establishes certain norms in social relations. It operates both within society at large and within different social groups. The activity and significance of public opinion are determined by the structural characteristics of society, the level of development of productive forces, culture, democratic legal norms, and freedoms. Public opinion is expressed in the election of government bodies, mass media, public surveys, and other forms of communication.

Key words: Public. Public opinion, methods of studying public opinion, mass opinion, goal setting, communication with society.

Introduction. In Uzbekistan, public relations and communication with the people have become an important social institution. Public opinion is like a mirror that reflects civil society, and this has been proven in practice. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized in his message to media workers on June 27, 2017, the Day of Press and Media Workers, "In today's world, where the aspirations, hopes, and concerns of the people are becoming part of state policy, only when each mass media outlet transforms into a genuine platform for communication and a forum for free expression can we achieve the goals we have set for ourselves."

Public opinion is the collection of people living in a specific area, group, or society. It reflects various opinions, values, and problems within that community. Public opinion is a form of public consciousness that shows the attitudes of different social groups toward current events and processes that affect their interests and needs. This phenomenon impacts various aspects of human life. It is the sum of individual opinions of specific persons or groups regarding a particular issue. This phenomenon is a balanced combination of psychological and social factors on various matters. It is expressed in evaluations (written, oral, printed) or public speeches. If the necessary

conditions for publicity are not present, the phenomenon can take disruptive forms. This perspective is reflected in the works of various authors and mass media and is generally accepted. Such a phenomenon can criticize or support government reforms and reflect the will of the people. Often, the process manifests itself in judgments that lead to actions. Sociology studies this phenomenon, considering the object of the phenomenon as specific issues or topics that can express a particular point of view. The participants in the discussion are the subjects from social groups.

Public opinion has existed since ancient times, dating back to the earliest eras. The term itself first appeared in England in the 12th century and gradually evolved into the phrase "public opinion." Its origins are linked to the activities of the English educator and writer John Salisbury, who first used it in his book *Polycraticon*.

The term entered the dictionaries of other countries from England. By the end of the 18th century, it became widely accepted. The first attempts to examine this process date back to the early 19th century, particularly in the works of English scholar Jeremy Bentham, who emphasized the significant role of this phenomenon in public life.

Public opinion was viewed as a means by which society could monitor government activities. In his works, Bentham gave particular attention to the press, seeing it as a tool for implementing this oversight. The press was considered a medium for expressing public opinion. The functions of this phenomenon were further studied and defined in the early 20th century.

Today, public opinion is one of the most important and multifaceted phenomena in modern life, significantly influencing the development and functioning of social infrastructure. Studying its core aspects is a central issue for various academic disciplines. It is not only the will of the people. In contemporary times, public opinion is a powerful tool used by politicians, party leaders, and organizational heads to implement their programs.

Public opinion is closely linked to the economic situation and the status of goods and services in the market. This phenomenon is becoming more pronounced with the emergence of various social issues. Reforms in the education system and changes in the personnel structure can serve as a basis for its development. Mass media are one of the tools for manipulating public opinion. Scholars identify several key functions of public opinion: expressive, evaluative, regulatory, consultative, directive, analytical, and constructive.

Modern sociologists consider the evaluative and regulatory functions as the primary roles of public opinion in human life.

1. Defining the Objectives What issues or topics do you want to study? For example, political, economic, social, or cultural issues.

2. Data Collection Methods. *Surveys:* A commonly used method in Uzbekistan and other countries. Surveys allow gathering opinions from a large audience. *Interviews:* Collecting in-depth information through open or closed-ended questions. *Focus Groups:* Gathering a group of people to discuss a specific topic. *Social Media Analysis:* Analyzing people's opinions and reactions on social media platforms.

3. Analysis Methods. *Qualitative Analysis:* Sorting the collected data into themes and conducting thematic analysis. *Quantitative Analysis:* Using statistical methods to quantify the data, creating graphs and diagrams.

4. Presenting the Results. Sharing the findings with the public through reports, presentations, or articles. This stage also involves considering the potential for changing or applying the results in practice.

5. Practical Application. Developing policies, marketing strategies, or social programs based on the findings.

6. Monitoring and Evaluation. Monitoring public opinion changes and assessing the impact of the research results.

Additional Sources. *Public Opinion Research Centers:* Various organizations and universities engage in public opinion research. *Articles and Books:* There are many academic works on social research and public opinion. Studying public opinion is an important tool for addressing social issues and improving society.

Conclusion. Public opinion is largely made up of people's desires, preferences, and views. It represents the collective opinion of a society or a nation on a particular issue or problem. Studying public opinion is a crucial process in social research, through which in-depth information about society's thoughts, attitudes, and needs can be gathered. The following key conclusions can be made: *Importance of Research:* Studying public opinion plays a vital role in making social, political, and economic decisions. Through this process, leaders and organizations can understand the needs of the public and respond accordingly. *Methods and Approaches:* Methods like surveys, interviews, focus groups, and social media analysis can be used to gather and analyze public opinion. *Data Analysis:* Data obtained through qualitative and quantitative analysis allows for a deeper understanding of the issues and trends within

society. **Practical Application of Results:** Monitoring changes in public opinion and applying research results in practice can lead to social change. **Communication with Society:** By studying public opinion, organizations and leaders can engage in effective communication with the public, helping to increase trust and ensure social stability. Overall, studying public opinion is an essential tool for societal development and ensuring social justice. The knowledge gained through this process is valuable not only in theory but also in practice.

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